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A FINSLER SPACE EQUIPPED WITH SEMI SYMMETRIC
CONNECTION COEFFICIENTS**

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PROJECTIVE CURVATURE COLLINEATION, SPECIAL PROJECTIVE MOTION AND CONFORMAL MOTION IN A FINSLER SPACE EQUIPPED WITH SEMI SYMMETRIC CONNECTION COEFFICIENTS

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Abstract : Katzin, Levine and Davis^[5] have defined curvature collineation in a Riemannian space and studied its properties. They also studied the properties of curvature collineations in conformally flat spaces. In a Finsler space the theory of curvature collineation have been studied by Singh and Prasad^[11], Pande and Kumar^[9], while carrying out such studies in a Finsler space they have taken into account Cartan's and Berwald's curvature tensors and have obtained the relations between curvature collineation and other symmetries admitted by the Finsler space. The present authors have discussed the theory of curvature collineation and also the theory of conformal motion with the help of curvature tensor type entity $R^i_{jkh}(x, \dot{x})$ depending on the semi-symmetric connection coefficient $\Pi^i_{hk}(x, \dot{x})$. In different sections of this paper, several relations between the curvature collineations, conformal motion and other symmetries admitted by such a Finsler space have been obtained.

Introduction : We give following definitions which shall be used in this discussion

Definition – 1 : Affine motion, Yano^[12].

A Finsler space F_n is said to admit an affine motion provided that there exists a vector $v^i(x)$ such that

$$\mathcal{L}_v G^i_{jk}(x, \dot{x}) = 0 \tag{1}$$

where G^i_{jk} is the Berwald's connection coefficient.

Definition - 2 : In Finsler space F_n , if the Berwald's curvature tensor field $H^i_{hjk}(x, \dot{x})$ satisfies the relation

$$H^i_{hjk(m)} = 0 \quad (2)$$

then such a Finsler space is called a symmetric Finsler space, Pande and Kumar^[9]. In view of equation (2), the following relations can also be obtained

$$\text{a) } H^i_{jk(m)} = 0, \quad \text{b) } H^i_{j(m)} = 0, \quad \text{c) } H_{(m)} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Projective Curvature Collineation in a Finsler Space Equipped with Semi-Symmetric Connection : Let us consider an infinitesimal point transformation

$$\bar{x}^i = x^i + v^i(x)d\zeta \quad (4)$$

where $v^i(x)$ determines a non-zero contravariant vector field defined over the domain of the space under consideration and $d\zeta$ is an infinitesimal constant.

Definition - 3 : The infinitesimal point transformation (4) defines a projective curvature collineation in a Finsler space equipped with semi-symmetric connection provided the space under consideration admits a vector field $v^i(x)$ such that

$$\mathcal{L}_v R^i_{jkh} = 0 \quad (5)$$

The curvature type quantities R^i_{jkh} introduced here are quite different than the curvature defined by the same notation of Rund^[10].

Definition - 4 : The Finsler space equipped with semi-symmetric connection is said to admit a Ricci type projective curvature collineation if there exists a vector field $v^i(x)$ such that

$$\mathcal{L}_v R_{kh} = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $R_{kh} = R^i_{ikh}$.

Definition - 5 : The infinitesimal point transformation (4) defines a special projective motion in a Finsler space equipped with semi-symmetric connection (to be denoted by F_n^+) if the Lie derivative of the semi-symmetric connection $\Pi_{jk}^i(x, \dot{x})$ with (2.1) itself has the form

$$\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{jk}^i(x, \dot{x}) = \delta_j^i \epsilon_k + \delta_k^i \epsilon_j \tag{7}$$

where ϵ_k is any non-zero covariant vector and satisfies the relation

$$\epsilon_k \dot{x}^k = 0 \tag{8}$$

We shall derive the conditions under which a special projective motion becomes a projective curvature collineation in a Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection. The Lie-derivative of $R_{hjk}^i(x, \dot{x})$ assumes the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_v R_{hjk}^i &= \zeta_k (\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{hj}^i) - \zeta_j (\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{hk}^i) - \Pi_{rhj}^i (\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{tk}^r) \dot{x}^t + \\ &+ \Pi_{rhk}^i (\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{tj}^r) \dot{x}^t \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where ζ_k stands for differentiation with respect to semi-symmetric connection. We use (7) in (9) and get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_v R_{hjk}^i &= \delta_h^i (\zeta_k \epsilon_j - \zeta_j \epsilon_k) + \delta_j^i (\zeta_k \epsilon_h) - \delta_k^i (\zeta_j \epsilon_h) - \\ &- \epsilon_k \Pi_{hj}^i + \epsilon_j \Pi_{hk}^i, \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where we have written $\Pi_{rhk}^i \dot{x}^r = \Pi_{hk}^i$ and have taken into account (8). If we now suppose that the special projective motion described in the space F_n^+ is also a special projective collineation then with the help of (5) and (10), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_h^i (\zeta_k \epsilon_j - \zeta_j \epsilon_k) + \delta_j^i (\zeta_k \epsilon_h) - \delta_k^i (\zeta_j \epsilon_h) - \\ - \epsilon_k \Pi_{hj}^i + \epsilon_j \Pi_{hk}^i = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

We now contract (11) with respect to the indices i and k and get

$$n\zeta_j \epsilon_h - \zeta_h \epsilon_j + \epsilon_i \Pi_{hj}^i - \epsilon_j \Pi_{hi}^i = 0. \quad (12)$$

Therefore, we can state the following :

Theorem - 1 : In a Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection if a special projective motion becomes a special projective collineation then (12) necessarily holds.

We assume that the non-zero covariant vector appearing in (7) is a covariant constant then under this assumption (12) can alternatively be written as

$$\epsilon_i \Pi_{hj}^i - \epsilon_j \Pi_{hi}^i = 0 \quad (13)$$

Hence, we can state :

Lemma - 1 : In the Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection if the covariant vector appearing in (7) be assumed to be a covariant constant then (13) necessarily holds.

We now contract (10) with respect to the indices i and h and get

$$\mathcal{L}_v R_{ijk}^i = \mathcal{L}_v R_{jk} = (n+1)\zeta_k \epsilon_j - 2n \zeta_j \epsilon_k + \epsilon_j \Pi_{ik}^i - \epsilon_k \Pi_{ij}^i \quad (14)$$

If we now assume that the space under consideration admits a Ricci type collineations then from (14), we get

$$(n+1)\zeta_k \epsilon_j - 2n \zeta_j \epsilon_k + \epsilon_j \Pi_{ik}^i - \epsilon_k \Pi_{ij}^i = 0. \quad (15)$$

Therefore, we can state :

Theorem - 2 : In a Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection if the special projective motion becomes a Ricci type projective curvature collineation then (15) necessarily holds.

At this stage, if we again suppose that non-zero vector ϵ_k appearing in (7) is a covariant constant then under this assumption (15) can alternatively be written as

$$\epsilon_j \Pi_{ik}^i - \epsilon_k \Pi_{ij}^i = 0. \quad (16)$$

with the help of (16), we can therefore state the following :

Lemma - 2 : In a Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection if a special projective motion becomes a special projective curvature collineation then (16) always holds provided the covariant vector appearing in (7) be assumed to be a covariant constant.

Conformal Motion in a Finsler Space F_n^+ Equipped with Semi-Symmetric

Connection : We say that the Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection defines a conformal motion if

$$\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{jk}^i = \delta_j^i \epsilon_k + \delta_k^i \epsilon_j - \epsilon^i g_{jk}, \tag{17}$$

where $\epsilon^i(x)$ is a non-zero vector field and satisfies the relation

$$\text{a) } \epsilon^i = g^{ik} \epsilon_k, \text{ b) } \epsilon_k = \partial_k \epsilon, \text{ c) } \mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{jk}^i = \epsilon_k \dot{x}^i - \epsilon^i g_{jk} \dot{x}^j. \tag{18}$$

We shall now investigate the circumstances under which a conformal motion given by (17) becomes a curvature collineation. In view of (17), the commutation form

$$\zeta_k (\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{hj}^i) \zeta_j (\mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{hk}^i) = \mathcal{L}_v R_{hjk}^i + \dot{x}^r \Pi_{rhj}^i \mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{tk}^r - \dot{x}^r \Pi_{rhk}^i \mathcal{L}_v \Pi_{tj}^r.$$

assumes the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_v R_{hjk}^i &= \zeta_k (\delta_h^i \epsilon_j + \delta_j^i \epsilon_h - \epsilon^i g_{hj}) - \\ &\quad - \zeta_j (\delta_h^i \epsilon_k + \delta_k^i \epsilon_h - \epsilon^i g_{hk}) - \\ &\quad - \Pi_{hj}^i \epsilon_k + \Pi_{hk}^i \epsilon_j + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi_{rhj}^i \dot{x}^r - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi_{rhk}^i \dot{x}^r. \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

We shall now make two different assumptions, one that the covariant vector ϵ_k appearing in (17) is a covariant constant and the other that the covariant vector ϵ_k of (17) is a covariant constant and also that the fundamental tensor is metrical, then under these two assumptions, we have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_v R_{hjk}^i &= \epsilon^i (\zeta_j g_{hk} - \zeta_k g_{hj}) + g_{hk} (\zeta_j \epsilon^i) - g_{hk} (\zeta_j \epsilon^i) - \\ &\quad - \Pi_{hj}^i \epsilon_k + \Pi_{hk}^i \epsilon_j + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi_{rhj}^i \dot{x}^r - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi_{rhk}^i \dot{x}^r \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

and
$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_v R^i_{hjk} = g_{hk} (\zeta_j \epsilon^i) - g_{hj} (\zeta_k \epsilon^i) - \Pi^i_{hj} \epsilon_k + \Pi^i_{hk} \epsilon_j + \\ + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi^i_{rhj} \dot{x}^\ell - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi^i_{rkh} \dot{x}^\ell. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Introducing (4) in (19), (20) and (21), we respectively get

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_k (\delta^i_h \epsilon_j + \delta^i_j \epsilon_h - \epsilon^i g_{hj}) - \zeta_j (\delta^i_h \epsilon_k + \delta^i_k \epsilon_h - \epsilon^i g_{hk}) - \\ - \Pi^i_{hj} \epsilon_k + \Pi^i_{hk} \epsilon_j + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi^i_{rhj} \dot{x}^\ell - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi^i_{rkh} \dot{x}^\ell = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon^i (\zeta_j g_{hk} - \zeta_k g_{hj}) + g_{hk} (\zeta_j \epsilon^i) - g_{hj} (\zeta_k \epsilon^i) - \Pi^i_{hj} \epsilon_k + \\ + \Pi^i_{hk} \epsilon_j + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi^i_{rhj} \dot{x}^\ell - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi^i_{rkh} \dot{x}^\ell = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

and
$$\begin{aligned} g_{hk} (\zeta_j \epsilon^i) - g_{hj} (\zeta_k \epsilon^i) - \Pi^i_{hj} \epsilon_k + \Pi^i_{hk} \epsilon_j + \\ + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi^i_{rhj} \dot{x}^\ell - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi^i_{rkh} \dot{x}^\ell = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

We now contract (22), (23) and (24) with respect to the indices i and j and get

$$\begin{aligned} (n+1)(\zeta_k \epsilon_h) - \zeta_h \epsilon_k - \zeta_k (\epsilon^i g_{hi}) + \zeta_i (\epsilon^i g_{hk}) - \\ - \Pi^i_{hi} \epsilon_k + \Pi^i_{hk} \epsilon_i + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi^i_{rhi} \dot{x}^\ell - \epsilon^r g_{ti} \Pi^i_{rkh} \dot{x}^\ell = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_i (\epsilon^i g_{hk}) - \zeta_k (\epsilon^i g_{hi}) - \Pi^i_{hi} \epsilon_k + \Pi^i_{hk} \epsilon_i + \\ + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi^i_{rhi} \dot{x}^\ell - \epsilon^r g_{ti} \Pi^i_{rkh} \dot{x}^\ell = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

and
$$\begin{aligned} g_{hk} (\zeta_k \epsilon^i) g_{hi} - (\zeta_k \epsilon^i) - \Pi^i_{hi} \epsilon_k + \Pi^i_{hk} \epsilon_i + \\ + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi^i_{rhi} \dot{x}^\ell - \epsilon^r g_{ti} \Pi^i_{rkh} \dot{x}^\ell = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

In the light of these observations, we can therefore state the following:

Theorem – 3 : If a Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection admits a conformal motion and curvature collineation respectively characterised by (17) and (5) then the equation (25) necessarily holds.

Theorem – 4 : If a Finsler space F_n^+ (equipped with semi-symmetric connection) admitting a conformal motion and a curvature collineation respectively characterised by (17) and (5), if the non zero vector ϵ_i appearing in (17) be assumed to be a covariant constant then equation (26) necessarily holds.

Theorem – 5 : If a Finsler space F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection admitting a conformal motion and a curvature collineation respectively characterised by (17) and (5), if the non zero vector ϵ_i appearing in (17) be a covariant constant and the fundamental tensor be assumed to be metrical then (27) holds necessarily.

We now contract (19) with respect to the indices i and h and get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_v R_{jk}^i = \mathcal{L}_v R_{jk} &= (n+1)\zeta_{[k} \epsilon_{j]} - \zeta_{[k} \epsilon^i g_{<i>j]} - \\ &- \Pi_{ij}^i \epsilon_k + \Pi_{ik}^i \epsilon_j + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi_{rij}^i \dot{x}^l - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi_{rjk}^i \dot{x}^l. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Therefore, we can state the following :

Theorem – 6 : If an F_n^+ equipped with semi-symmetric connection admits a conformal motion and a Ricci type curvature collineation respectively characterised by (17) and (6) then we shall always have

$$\begin{aligned} (n+1)\zeta_{[k} \epsilon_{j]} - \zeta_{[k} \epsilon^i g_{<i>j]} - \Pi_{ij}^i \epsilon_k + \Pi_{ik}^i \epsilon_j + \\ + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi_{rij}^i \dot{x}^l - \epsilon^r g_{tj} \Pi_{rjk}^i \dot{x}^l = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

At this stage, we make the supposition that the covariant vector appearing in (17) is a covariant constant and also that the fundamental tensor is metrical, then under these two suppositions we can get the following from (29).

$$g_{ik}(\zeta_j \epsilon^i) - g_{ij}(\zeta_k \epsilon^i) - \Pi'_{ij} \epsilon_k + \Pi'_{ik} \epsilon_j + \\ + \epsilon^r g_{tk} \Pi'_{rij} \dot{x}^l - \epsilon^r g_{ij} \Pi'_{rik} \dot{x}^l = 0. \quad (30)$$

Thus, we can state :

Theorem - 7 : In a Finsler space F_n^+ (equipped with semi-symmetric connection) admitting a conformal motion and a Ricci type curvature collineation respectively characterised by (17) and (6) if the non-zero vector ϵ_k appearing in (17) be a covariant constant and the fundamental tensor be assumed to be metrical then we shall always have (30).

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